

An Interpretation on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and its Relationship with Craft Based SHGs Activities in India

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Abstract

Craft is an art, trade, or occupation required special skills, especially manual skills that can be reproduced in a skilful way at a mass scale which is conducive to make women economically empowered. The concept of empowerment is involved within three closely interrelated areas like agency, resources and performance. Gender equality, rural development with expansion of education through various Craft based Self Help Groups (SHGs) activities and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are important techniques to reduce poverty and create income and employment opportunities taking into consideration of maintaining livelihood. Statistical data focus that a large number of women in India are mainly involved in subsistence agriculture and small scale enterprises. SHGs attempt to make them self-reliant and self-confident from the point of view of income generating activities. So, the present study has attempted to undertake 'An Interpretation on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and its Relationship with Craft Based SHGs Activities in India'. The study represents that MSMEs and Craft based activities play a pivotal role in order to attain women economically empowered.

Key Words: Craft, SHGs, MSMEs, Livelihood, Women Empowerment, Poverty, Income, Rural Development and Education.

Introduction:

Craft is an art, trade, or occupation required special skills, especially manual skills that can be reproduced in a skilful way at a mass scale which is conducive to make women economically empowered. The concept of empowerment is involved within three closely interrelated areas like agency, resources and performance. Gender equality, rural development with expansion of education through various Craft based SHG activities and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are important techniques to reduce poverty and create income and employment opportunities largely. A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets and activities required for a means of living. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stresses and shocks and maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets both now and in the future, while not undermining the natural base. A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets (Natural, Physical, Human, Financial, and social Capital) and activities required for the means of living (Chambers and Conway, 1992). Rural development activities focus on infrastructure development, education and health service, investment in agriculture and boosting of rural non-farm activities. Statistical data focus that a large number of women in India are mainly involved in subsistence agriculture and small scale enterprise. One of the major constraints women face as entrepreneurs is the unequal access to productive resources and services taking into consideration of finance and skill upgrading opportunities. Over the years, NABARD, Govt. agencies and the non-government organizations have been undertaking

various skilful training and livelihood related activities providing credit and motivation for stakeholders. SHGs attempted to make them self-reliant and self-confident from the point of view of income generating activities. NABARD(SHGs,2019) reported some income generating craft based activities like Kadhi weaving, decorative items from coconut coir,Diary,Terracotta , manufacture of jute bags ,Tailoring, organic farming, dress materials, food processing , detergent etc. So, the present study has attempted to undertake 'An Interpretation on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and its Relationship with Craft Based SHGs Activities in India'.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out various Craft Based SHGs Activities taking into consideration of women empowerment in study areas and India.
- To estimate the scope of employment and income generation opportunities under craft based activities and Micro, Small, Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the study areas and India.

Methodology:

The study is based on some field survey observation from district of Birbhum, West Bengal and secondary data have been purposively collected from published reports like NABARD (2019), Journals, Report on Informal Sector (GOI) and Annual Report, 2020-21, Ministry of Micro, Small, Medium Enterprises, GOI etc. The collected data have analysed on the basis of tabular form and figures following nature of activities, socio-

economic impact and scope of employment and income creation etc.

Results and discussion:

Importance and Functions of Women Enterprise:

- A good share of population.
- Traditionally outside the domain of economic activities.
- They must be made part of the economic development because it will ensure the economic and social development of the women along with providing more human resources to strengthen the economy of the country.
- The economic status of women is now accepted as indicators of a society's stage of development.
- Functions of Women Entrepreneur may be stated as
 - (i) Motivation, (ii) Leadership, (iii) Directing, (iv) Staffing, (v)Organizing, (vi)Planning, (vii)Coordination, (viii)Supervision:

Socio-economic Activities of SHG:

A small economically homogeneous and affinity group of rural poor who have come together voluntarily. SHGs attempt to carry out the following activities.

- (i) To save small amounts regularly , (ii) to mutually agree to contribute to a common fund,(iii) conflict solving through collective leadership and mutual discussion, (iv) to meet their emerging needs, (v) have simple and responsive Rules, (vi) collated free loans with term decided by the group, (vii)market driven Rates of Interest, (viii) collective decision making

Socio-economic Significance of SHGs in India:

Socio-economic significance of SHGs may be focused in the following aspects

- (i) Improve efficiency of the credit system, (ii) Channel of financial conclusion, (iii) Resource mobilization, (iv) Promote savings and banking habit, (v) Improve the living condition of the poor, (vi) Empowerment of women, (vii) Promote social and economic justice, (viii) Community actions, (ix) Develop individual skills, (x) Livelihood finance and employment generation, (xi) Reduce influence of unorganized sector, Xii) Beneficial to the financial sector.

Some obstacles of Women Entrepreneurship in India and its measures:

- Lack of self -confidence
- Will-power
- Strong mental outlook
- Optimistic attitude
- Women India lead a protected life,
- The old and outdated social outlook to resist women from entering in the field of entrepreneurship.
- The educational level and family background of husbands also influences women participation in the field of enterprise.
- Absence of proper support, cooperation and back-up for women by their own family members.
- Lack of awareness about the financial assistance in the form of incentives, training, loans, schemes tec.
- Lack of women mobility
- Some steps by India Government: IRDP, KVIC, TRYSEM, PMRY, EDPs, WDCs, ARWIND,
- TREAD, MAHIMA, MSE-CDP, Mahila Samiti Yojana, Micro Credit Scheme

Table- 1: Comparative distribution of top ten states

Sl. No	State/UT	NSS 73 rd round*	Share (%)	Fourth All India Census of MSME and Fifth Economic Census*	Share (%)
		Number(in lakh)		Number(in lakh)	
1.	Uttar Pradesh	89.99	14	44.03	12
2.	West Bengal	88.67	14	34.64	10
3.	Tamil Nadu	49.48	8	33.13	9
4.	Maharashtra	47.78	8	30.63	8
5.	Karnataka	38.34	6	20.19	6
6.	Bihar	34.46	5	14.70	4
7.	Andra Pradesh***	33.87	5	25.96	7
8.	Gujarat	33.16	5	21.78	6
9.	Rajasthan	26.87	4	16.64	5
10	Madhya Pradesh	26.74	4	19.33	5
11.	Total of above ten States	469.4	74	261.04	72
12.	Other State/ UTs	164.5	26	100.72	28
13.	All	633.9	100	361.76	10

Source: *NSS Round, 2015-16, ** Fourth All India Census of MSME, 2006-07(Unregistered Sector) and Fifth

Economic Census, *** Including Telagana in Fourth All India Census of MSME

Table-1 brings out about state-wise distribution of estimated MSMEs and share(%) according to NSS 73rd round taking into account of higher estimated number of MSMEs 88.99 lakh (14 %) in Uttar Pradesh, followed by 88.67 lakh(14 %) in West Bengal, 49.48 lakh(8 %) in Tamil Nadu 38.34 lakh(6 %) in Karnata, 34.46 Lakh(5 %) in Bihar,

33.87 lakh(5 %) in Andhra Pradesh, 33.16 lakh (5 %) in Gujarat, 26.87 lakh (4 %) in Madhya Pradesh, 164.52 lakh (26 %) in others . The secondary data in table-2 show that top ten states in India play a pivotal role in creation of employment generation(72%) as compared to other states/UTs(28%) and making good economic health of the country.

Table-2: Percentage Distribution of Enterprises in Rural and Urban areas (Male/Female ownership)

Sector	Male	Female	All
Rural	77.76	22.24	100
Urban	81.58	18.42	100
All	79.63	20.37	100

(Source:Annual Report 2021-22, Annual Report, 2020-21, Ministry of Micro, Small and medium Enterprises, GOI GOI)

Table-2 exhibits % distribution of enterprises in rural and urban areas (male/female ownership) and estimate higher % of urban enterprises owned by male (81.58 %) as compared to rural enterprises owned by male. % distribution of enterprises owned by male in both rural(77.76 %) and urban(81.58 %)

measures more higher as compared to that of female in rural(22.24 %) and urban(18.42 %). For all India, % distribution of enterprises owned by male shows more higher (79.63 %) as compared to the of female (20.37 %).

Figure--1: Khadi Sector's employment during last 4 years and current year 2021-22 are given below.

(Source: Annual Report 2021-22, Annual Report, 2020-21, Ministry of Micro, Small and medium Enterprises, GOI GOI)

Figure-1 delineates khadi sector's employment(artisan in Lakh) during last 4 year and current year 2021-22 and give an account of employment generation as 4.65 lakh in 2017-18 , followed by 4.96 lakh in 4.96 in 2018-19, 4.97 lakh

in 2019-20, 4.97 lakh in 2020-21, 4.97 lakh in 2021-22 and 4.97 lakh (Projected up to 31-03-2022). So, Kadhi Sector attempts to create a gainful employment generation during last 4 years and current year 2021-22.

Figure-2: Village Industries: Employment (Artisan in Lakh) during 2017-18 to 2021-22

(Source: Annual Report 2021-22, GOI)

Figure-2 reveals village industry indicating any industry of village industry which is located in the rural area and attempts to produce any good or render any service with or without using electricity and which creates employment to one artisan or labour by investment of fixed capital amount of Rs 50, 000. It is found from the table that village industries create higher employment (artisan in Lakh) during 2017-18 to 2021-22.

Some Employment and Income Generation Activities conducted by SHGs;

(1) Weaving Activity: Weaving by SHG members at Maharipara, Baksa District, Assam.

Nature of Activity: Under NABARD's Micro Enterprise Development programme (MED) involving a grant assistance of Rs. 0.50 lakh, 24 beneficiaries from different SHGs were provided 13 days' skill development and skill upgradation training in weaving.

Impact: Income Rs 3,000/ weaver /month.

Earlier, a weaver would earn Rs 1800/ - 3000/ a month from selling traditional garments, shawls and clothes used by womenfolk. Since they have upgraded their skills, they are able to produce products in vogue using new designs and superior quality. Their income has now increased by more than 30 %.(Source: SHGs- Creating Likelihoods, Changing Lives, NABARD, 2019).

(2). Nai Roshni is an SHG supported by NABARD and promote by Abhivakti Foundation in Banchari Village, Palwal District, Haryana.

Activity: Terracotta ware, viz , designers plates, lamps, flower pots, water bottles , cups, utensils.

Nature of Activity: The members were adept potters and with proper training they were producing

Lakh) taking into account 159.10 in 2021-22(up to 31-12-2021), followed by 154.09 in 2020-21, 147.76 in 2019-20, 142.03 in 2018-19, 135.71 in 2017-18 and 161.47 employment(artisan in Lakh) in 2021-22(Projected up to 31-03-2022).So, village industries create a gainful employment(Artisan in Lakh) during 2017-18 to 2021-22.

artisanal quality products but they confined to their own village and few regulars in and around their district.

Impact: The monthly turnover of the group is approximately Rs 1.0 lakh by rendering to the demands of domestic and foreign clients (Source: SHGs- Creating Likelihoods, Changing Lives, NABARD, 2019).

(3) Activity: Candle Making

Nature of activity: Candle making by Pragati SHG, Chaproli Baghpat district, Uttar Pradesh. 11 women members of Pragati SHG were trained in Candle making by Arpit Gramudyog Sansthan with a grant assistance of Rs. 1 lakh from NABARD for the group.

Economic Impact: Income: Rs 10,000- 30,000/ per member/month (Source: SHGs- Creating Likelihoods, Changing Lives, NABARD, 2019).

(4) Activity: Making Coconut Broom (Coconut broom is made by extracting the stems of the leaves from a coconut palm tree.

Location: Annapurnapalli, Bolpur, Birbhum, West Bengal, India

Nature of Activity: It is family based enterprise started about 50 years ago by Late Paban Patra. Raw materials come from Hooghly, Burdwan and

Midnapur. The market demand for Coconut broom is good and it is supplied to local market. It is produced all year round, but more for four month (July, August, Sept, Octo). No Bank Loan is taken.

Income – Rs 4000/-5000/ per month/ worker.

Family Income: Rs 30,000/ month (Source: Field Survey)

Impact: This enterprise helps to sustain livelihood. Five members are involved in the activity and out of five, three are contract basis workers.

Fig-3: Making Coconut Broom

(5) Activity: Full Broom Making

Nature of Activity: Material comes from Assam, Nepal. It is made through the year. Its market demand is very good.

Name of Owner: Susanta Kundu. Family based business. No bank loan is taken.

Impact: Three workers are engaged in making full broom.

Family Income: Rs 25,000/per month. (Source: Field Survey)

Fig-4: Full Broom Making

Conclusion:

Craft is tangible object produced by the craftsman manually with a well defined goal using his creative abilities. Craft is an art, trade, or occupation requiring special skills, especially manual skills that can be reproduced, in skillful way at a mass scale. The concept of empowerment is involved within three closely interrelated areas like agency, resources and performance. Gender equality and rural development through various Craft based SHG social activities are important techniques to reduce poverty and create income and employment opportunities. Statistical data focus that a large number of women are mainly involved in subsistence agriculture and small scale enterprise (MSE). SHGs do have a potential to create an empowered and competitive position in the market

through its services and dispel poverty and derivation. One of the major constraints women face as entrepreneur is the unequal access to productive resources and services taking into consideration of finance and skill upgrading opportunities. SHGs attempted to make them self-reliant and self-confident from the point of view of income generating activities. The Sixth Five –Year Plan (1980-85) saw a definite shift from welfare to development. It recognized women's lack of access to resources as a critical factor impeding their growth. Women Entrepreneur is a person who accepts challenges role to meet her personal need and become economically independent. Major findings of the study may stated as follows:

- Top ten states in India play a pivotal role in creation of employment generation(72 %) as

compared to other states/ UTs(28%) and attempt in making good economic health of the country

- Women's family and personal obligations are sometimes a great barrier for succeeding in business carrier.
- The activities conducted by MSMEs were labour intensive.
- % distribution of enterprises owned by male in both rural(77.76 %) and urban(81.58 %) measures more higher as compared to that of female in rural(22.24 %) and urban(18.42 %).
- For all India, % distribution of enterprises owned by male shows more higher (79.63 %) as compared to the of female (20.37 %).
- SHG activities are associated with skill training at local level following training on scientific methods
- Members of SHGs are oriented maintaining quality of the products and development of better entrepreneurship skills.
- The Members of various SHGs have been completely changed their lives through activities by enhancing family income and education of their children.
- It is imperative to provide sustainable interventions from Government required for better designs, skills and technology up gradation and market development.

References:

1. Chambers, R and Conway, G. (1992). Sustainable Rural Livelihoods: Practical Concepts for the 21st Century; Institute of Development Studies: Brighton, UK.
2. Carney, D (1999). Approaches to Sustainable Livelihoods for the Rural poor; ODI poverty Briefing; Overseas Development Institute: Brighton, UK.
3. Centre for Civil Society (2014). Study of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Princy Saini. Researching Reality Summer Internship 2014, Working Paper, 319.www.ccs.in
4. Department for International Development (1999). Sustainable Rural Livelihoods Guidance Sheets; Department for International Development, UK.
5. Government of India (2013). Annual report. Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Government of India. Udyog Bhavan, New Delhi-110107. www.msme.gov.in
6. Government of India (2015). Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (An ISO 9001: 2008 Certified Organization). Udyog Bhawan, New Delhi-110011.
7. Government of India (2021). Annual Report, 2021-22. Government of India. Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.
8. Mandal, A.K.(2022).An Analysis of Employment Generation through MSMEs and its Integration with Sustainable Development (SD) Goals. Journal of Research and Development, A Multidisciplinary International Level Referred Journal, June, 2022, Vol.14, Issue-5, Impact Factor: 7.265, ISSN-2230-9578, pp.141-147.
9. Micro Credit Innovation Department (2019). SHGs- Creating Likelihoods, Changing Lives, NABARD. Plot No.C-24, 'G' Block, BKC, Bandra (E). Mumbai-400051. www.nabard.org
10. Report on Employment in Informal Sector and Conditions of Informal Employment: 2013-14, Volume IV)(Govt. of India , Ministry of Labour & Employment, Labour Bureau, Chandigarh.